

TOWARDS
A NATIONAL
COLLECTION

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COMMISSIONED REPORT

Towards a National Collection: Total Economic Value of a unified digital collection

July 2024

Authored by Alma Economics

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About the authors

Alma Economics combines unparalleled analytical expertise with the ability to communicate complex ideas clearly.

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Executive Summary

Alma Economics was commissioned by Towards a National Collection (TaNC) to estimate the Total Economic Value of a future unified digital collection of cultural heritage assets in the UK.¹ The outputs from this work will be used to provide evidence to feed into the business case for funding for a UK digital collections infrastructure.

Our approach involved the deployment of contingent valuation surveys to elicit respondents' willingness to pay for a hypothetical unified digital collection of cultural heritage assets.^{2,3} The surveys were rolled out to three distinct groups to test how respondents' valuations varied depending on the nature and extent of individuals' interest in and engagement with cultural heritage, namely:

- a. **The general population**, consisting of individuals with either a general interest in cultural heritage collections or no or little demonstrable interest in these collections.
- b. **Academics and researchers** who might use the unified digital collection as part of their research, including those specialising in fields directly related to cultural heritage as well as adjacent subjects such as in the humanities.
- c. **Individuals with a "special interest" in cultural heritage**, who were identified through referrals from cultural heritage organisations.

Our analysis found that the service was valued to differing extents by each of these three groups, with headline findings presented below.

General population findings

Our analysis of questionnaires completed by over 8,000 individuals from the general population found an average **willingness to pay (in terms of an increase in annual taxes) of around £8 per person** to support the development, maintenance, and free accessibility of a unified digital collection of cultural heritage assets for the UK. By extrapolating this finding to the full UK adult population, we estimate a **Total Economic Value for the service of around £425m per annum**.

Respondents indicated a range of reasons for valuing the service, including reasons related to their use of the service (i.e., having an interest in viewing cultural heritage online and the service providing access to assets they would not otherwise be able to see), as well as perceiving value in the existence of the service regardless of their level of use of it (i.e., preserving cultural heritage for future generations and improving access to the assets for society more widely). Those who did not value the service did so for reasons including not expecting

¹ In this context, the Total Economic Value method is an analytical approach that seeks to estimate the complete worth of a unified digital collection by considering both the market (aspects that have a direct market price) and non-market (such as intrinsic value or cultural significance) values.

² For the purposes of this study, cultural heritage includes assets held as part of the collections of museums, galleries, libraries, and archives (a detailed description can be found on Page 7).

³ Contingent valuation is an economic valuation method which seeks to estimate the value of a good or service by asking people directly how much they would be willing to pay for it.

to use the service or due to concerns around the size of the benefits the service would yield, whilst some respondents objected to the principle of the service being funded through general taxation.

Academics and researchers findings

Analysis of survey questionnaires completed by 326 academics and researchers found an **average willingness to pay for the proposed service (in terms of a monthly subscription to access the service) of around £13 per person per month.**

Reasons put forward by academics and researchers for a positive valuation of the service commonly related to their professional use of the service (i.e., for use in education and research, and opening new lines of research) and its value for more general purposes (i.e., an interest in accessing digital cultural heritage assets online and having access to assets they would not otherwise be able to see). Those who reported a zero valuation for the service often did so because of doubts around the usefulness of the service, whilst some respondents also objected to paying for access via a subscription model on the basis that the service should be free and open to access.

Special interest individuals findings

The analysis of 267 survey responses completed by individuals with a special interest in digital cultural heritage found an **average willingness to pay for the service (in terms of a monthly subscription to access the service) of around £3 per person per month.**

Respondents who valued the service often did so because they viewed there to be benefits in using the service (i.e., for research or educational purposes), as well as perceived value in the existence of the service regardless of their level of use of it (i.e., preserving cultural heritage for future generations and improving access to the assets for society more widely). Those who provided a zero valuation for the service often did so because they objected to paying for access via a subscription model on the basis that the service should be free and open to access, whilst others did so because of doubts around the usefulness of the service.

Background

About Towards a National Collection

The Arts and Humanities Research Council's (AHRC) Strategic Priorities Fund has funded 34 programmes involving multi- and interdisciplinary research organised under eight themes.⁴ Towards a National Collection (TaNC) is one of the two projects funded within the funding's digital theme, having been awarded £18.9m to run from 2020 to 2025.

TaNC aims to take the first steps towards creating a unified virtual national collection of the UK's museums, archives, libraries, and galleries by dissolving barriers between different collections⁵. The programme's main objectives are:

- to begin to dissolve barriers between different collections;
- to open up collections to new cross-disciplinary and cross-collection lines of research;
- to extend researcher and public access beyond the physical boundaries of their location;
- to benefit a diverse range of audiences;
- to be active and of benefit across the UK;
- to provide clear evidence and exemplars that support enhanced funding going forward.

Specifically, TaNC aims to have a transformative impact on:

- Digital search and cataloguing tools for collections, and related technologies and methodologies.
- Research capability: through enhanced researcher access and new cross-collection search tools, researchers will be able to exploit the potential of the nation's research assets in innovative ways, addressing radically new research questions and thereby maintaining UK global leadership in interdisciplinary research.
- Public access and public engagement with heritage: the programme will generate research-driven public-facing outputs, including major new exhibitions and immersive installations; extend public access beyond collections' physical locations, nationally and internationally; and facilitate wider and better-informed public engagement.

TaNC has awarded grants for research and development projects in three tranches – eight 'Foundation Projects', three 'Covid-19 Projects' and five large-scale 'Discovery Projects'. Projects are carried out by a combination of organisations, including UK higher education institutions, independent research organisations, and cultural organisations.

⁴ UKRI Strategic Priorities Fund. See: <https://www.ukri.org/what-we-do/strategic-priorities-fund/>

⁵ Towards a National Collection. See: <https://www.nationalcollection.org.uk/about>

Scope of this study

At the time of writing, discussions were underway – led by the Towards a National Collection Steering Committee – on the scoping of a UK digital collections research infrastructure, and the development of a case for funding beyond the current five-year programme to support that infrastructure. Key to that case will be the presentation of evidence relating to the Total Economic Value of digital cultural heritage collections and the return on investment from that infrastructure.

Alma Economics was commissioned by TaNC to measure the Total Economic Value of a future unified digital collection to inform the business case for funding a UK digital collections infrastructure through robust evidence that adheres to the guidance described in HM Treasury’s Green Book.⁶ This work builds on a scoping study conducted by Human Economics, in collaboration with Ipsos, outlining a series of options for estimating the Total Economic Value of this service.⁷

Rationale for contingent valuation approach

Valuing access to cultural heritage assets presents unique challenges due to its predominantly intangible and non-market nature, that is, the fact that related assets and services are often not bought or sold on the open market by their users, thus providing limited evidence of their value. Cultural heritage collections typically qualify as non-market goods as they are generally not tradable, and thus an open market price for accessing them is typically not available.

A key component of the value of cultural heritage assets is the benefits they deliver to society, yet assessing these benefits presents considerable complexity, due to their subjective nature, which can drive substantial variation across individuals. For example, a unified digital collection of cultural heritage assets for the UK could unlock new research opportunities for academics and researchers, offer curators additional resources for exhibitions, or enable a London resident to explore artworks held in a museum in Glasgow without leaving their city. When assessing the public sector investment proposition for such assets, valuation methods should therefore aim to quantify the wide range of benefits that make up the economic value of cultural heritage assets.

Economic techniques for measuring the non-market benefits of culture and heritage assets are gaining increasing recognition amongst policymakers (Crossick & Kaszniska, 2016). The HM Treasury Green Book’s welfare approach sets out a framework for estimating the Total Economic Value of policies, programmes, and interventions, focusing not only on economic benefits like increased economic output or employment, but on broader (often intangible) societal benefits such as wellbeing, education, and community cohesion. Methodologies have also been developed to overcome the challenges of estimating the societal benefits of cultural heritage assets, crucial for evidencing the business cases for public policy programmes.

HM Treasury’s Green Book and DCMS’s Culture and Heritage Capital Framework provide guidance for valuing non-market goods, like cultural heritage assets, in monetary terms, with stated preference techniques being

⁶ The Green Book (2022). See: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/the-green-book-appraisal-and-evaluation-in-central-government/the-green-book-2020>

⁷ ‘Towards a National Collection – Total Economic Value Scoping Study’ (Human Economics, 2023, Unpublished).

one of the suggested families of methodologies for doing this.^{8,9} Within the class of stated preference methods, there are two alternative groups of techniques: choice modelling and contingent valuation. Contingent valuation focuses on the non-market good or service as a whole, while choice modelling seeks to understand preferences for individual characteristics or attributes of these goods and services to be valued. To estimate the value of a unified digital collection, contingent valuation is therefore the preferred method.

Contingent valuation studies utilise surveys that present relevant user groups with information about a given good or service. The aim is to derive the value of a good or service from how much respondents state they would be willing to pay to enjoy that good or service. This technique is known as “contingent valuation” as it involves asking respondents to indicate their values, contingent on there being a hypothetical market for that good or service.

The contingent valuation method offers a significant advantage in its ability to capture the a range of values associated with cultural heritage assets, including both use values and non-use values. Direct use values relate to actual or planned individual use of the asset, while indirect use values reflect benefits gained without direct interaction. Non-use values encompass existence value, appreciating the asset's mere existence; bequest value, reflecting the value of preserving it for future generations; and altruistic value, valuing the asset's availability to others who might directly benefit from it. Finally, both users and non-users may place an “option” value on the service, whereby they perceive there to be value in the option of being able to use the asset in the future. By directly eliciting the valuation of each individual, contingent valuation is in principle able to capture the full range of value associated with enabling access to cultural heritage assets.

⁸ Valuing culture and heritage capital: a framework towards informing decision making (2021): <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/valuing-culture-and-heritage-capital-a-framework-towards-decision-making/valuing-culture-and-heritage-capital-a-framework-towards-informing-decision-making>

⁹ Stated preference techniques are methods used in economics to directly elicit individuals' preferences and willingness to pay for goods or services through surveys or hypothetical scenarios.

Methodology

This contingent valuation study was implemented through a set of surveys designed to elicit the willingness to pay (WTP) of individuals for a unified digital collection of cultural heritage assets in the UK¹⁰. To reflect different uses and levels of engagement with cultural heritage, our study has sought to understand the willingness to pay for the proposed service from three distinct perspectives:

- **The general population**, consisting of individuals with either a general interest in cultural heritage collections (defined as having engaged with digital collections of cultural heritage assets in the past 12 months) or those with no or little demonstrable interest in these collections (defined as not having engaged with digital collections of cultural heritage assets in the past 12 months).
- **Academics and researchers** who might use the unified digital collection as part of their research, specialising in fields directly related to cultural heritage as well as adjacent subjects such as in the humanities.
- **Individuals with a “special interest” in cultural heritage**, including individuals with a substantial interest in cultural heritage collections, who were identified through referrals from cultural heritage organisations.

To comprehensively assess the value respondents would place on a unified digital collection of cultural heritage assets, and the reasons underlying each answer, we developed and rolled out three contingent surveys tailored to each of these groups. The diagram below summarises the main steps involved in delivering this study, with the rest of this section providing additional detail.

¹⁰ Our approach adapted and built on the recommendations provided by the scoping study conducted by Human Economics in collaboration with Ipsos.

Contingent valuation survey design

Consistent with best practice established by precedent literature (see the literature review in Appendix A), and guided by principles outlined in the HM Treasury Green Book supplementary guidance for Stated Preference techniques (Pearce & Özdemiroğlu, 2002), we developed a survey questionnaire which covered the following topics and themes:¹¹

1. Behavioural and attitudinal questions

Questions were developed to investigate respondents' behaviours and attitudes towards cultural heritage and digital collections. Common to all three respondent groups, these questions sought to gauge the nature and extent of respondents' engagement with cultural heritage, both in physical and digital form, and if they were members of cultural heritage organisations. Respondents were also asked to express their level of agreement or disagreement with a series of statements to reflect their attitudes towards the importance of preserving cultural heritage collections and supporting cultural heritage organisations.

2. Description of the service to be valued

All respondents were asked to read a written description of a unified digital collection of cultural heritage assets to be valued as part of the study. This description detailed the nature of cultural heritage assets held within museum, gallery, library and archive collections, followed by an overview of the proposed unified digital collection infrastructure, outlining its scope, purpose, and anticipated benefits. The description of the service agreed with TaNC and used in all three surveys is shown below:

"The UK has a wide range of cultural heritage assets, held as part of cultural heritage collections, examples of which include:

- *Works of art, including paintings, sculptures, photographs, and contemporary artworks.*
- *Artifacts, such as tools, jewellery, ceramics, clothing, and other items of historical significance.*
- *Books, manuscripts, and maps.*
- *Other archive materials, including film and television footage, music and audio recordings, newspapers, and magazines.*
- *Digital born assets, such as digital photographs and videos, digital audio recordings and digital artworks.*

These cultural heritage assets are held as part of the collections of museums, galleries, libraries, and archives. Many of these institutions provide some form of digital access to their collections. Nevertheless, these digital resources are spread across a large number of webpages maintained by their respective institutions.

This survey's objective is to understand the value of making available on a single online platform a combined digital collection held by museums, galleries, libraries, and archives across the UK. These collections comprise of digitised versions of physical assets – consisting of photos, videos, audio or 3D reproductions – as well as digital born assets,

¹¹ A copy of the survey questionnaire is available in Appendix F.

accompanied by information that describes the context and key characteristics of each of these assets.

This service would be presented in a user-friendly online experience that, harnessing the latest technological innovations, would allow users to seamlessly explore a large amount of assets from many digital cultural heritage collections through a single interface. These collections could include those of the largest and most renowned UK cultural heritage institutions, as well as those of smaller, more local organisations.

This service would be developed through a publicly funded investment programme, using digital technology to create a unified national collection of cultural heritage assets from the UK's museums, libraries, galleries, and archives."

3. Willingness to pay questions

A core element of the questionnaire was a set of willingness to pay questions designed to elicit a valuation from respondents for the proposed unified digital collection of cultural heritage assets. Based on insight from the literature and the testing phase, the willingness to pay questions were tailored to each respondent group, reflecting expected differences in the levels and types of engagement of each group with the service. Two key aspects were considered to enhance the reliability of respondents' valuations, ensuring the willingness to pay values provided by respondents were as close to their true valuation of the service as possible: (i) the mechanism for paying for the service,¹² and (ii) the method through which respondents' willingness to pay for the service was elicited.

Mechanisms for paying for the service

Depending on the respondent group, we used two broad options for framing how the service would be paid for by the respondent:

- **Monthly subscription service.** Participants in the academics/researchers and "special interest" groups, who were expected to have a more frequent and potentially professional use of the unified digital collection, were presented with a monthly subscription as the designated payment method.
- **Increase in annual tax payments.** Respondents from the general population were presented with an increase in annual taxes as the proposed payment vehicle. This approach was selected to reflect the anticipated less frequent use of the digital collection among the general population, whilst recognising the potential non-use value¹³ of this initiative.

Methods for eliciting each respondent's willingness to pay

Depending on the respondent group, we used two broad methods for eliciting each respondent's willingness to pay for the existence of the unified digital cultural heritage collection:

¹² The literature on contingent valuation typically utilises three broad options for payment mechanisms: a contribution out of general taxation, a regular subscription, or a lump sum donation.

¹³ Non-use value represents the benefits people derive from a good or service even when they don't actively use or consume it. In the case of a unified digital collection of UK cultural heritage assets, these benefits may arise, for example, from the appreciation that this service could make it easier for people around the world to understand the UK's cultural heritage, or that this service could advance knowledge by helping researchers explore new research questions.

- **Double-bounded dichotomous choice.** For the general population sample, willingness to pay was elicited using a double-bounded dichotomous choice (DBDC) method. This approach involves presenting respondents with two consecutive amounts and asking whether they would be willing to pay each amount to support the development, maintenance, and free accessibility of the unified digital collection. The first amount was randomly assigned from a set of predetermined values, whereas the second amount was selected based on participants' responses to the first amount presented (i.e., halving or doubling the initial value depending on if the respondent selected yes or no). This method allows for a more robust estimation of average willingness to pay, albeit necessitating a larger sample size to achieve statistically robust results. As a sense check for the DBDC approach, each participant was also asked to indicate the exact amount they would be willing to pay for access to the digital collection.
- **Payment card approach.** In the academics/researchers and "special interest" surveys, willingness to pay was elicited using a payment card approach, where respondents were presented with a set of predetermined monthly subscription amounts and asked to indicate which one was closest to their maximum willingness to pay. An open-ended "other" amount option was included to offer respondents more flexibility in expressing their valuation of the service.

4. Factors influencing willingness to pay

Respondents were asked about the reasons behind their stated willingness or unwillingness to pay for the unified digital collection of cultural heritage assets. Respondents who expressed a positive willingness to pay were presented with a list of factors and asked to select those that best explained their willingness to pay for the proposed service. These factors encompassed rationales that reflected both benefits to them as individuals (such as contributing to the research of academics or personal enjoyment) and broader societal benefits (such as the service contributing to preserving cultural heritage for future generations).

Respondents who indicated an unwillingness to pay for the service (as indicated by a £0 response regarding their willingness to pay for the service) were also asked to select reasons from a list of factors to explain the rationale behind this answer. The options presented covered a range of factors related to their preferences, personal circumstances, and practical considerations, including, for example, perceived lack of benefit, financial constraints, or simple lack of interest. Options were also included to identify "protest" responses, representing responses which valued the service at a lower amount than their true valuation of the underlying service on the basis of objection to the way the service was framed in the questionnaire (such as moral objections to funding the service through taxation or a subscription-based model).

5. Socio-demographic characteristics

To allow the willingness to pay estimates to be broken down across sub-categories of interest, respondents were also asked to provide information of their socio-demographic characteristics, such as their current region of residence, gender, age, ethnic background, education, and income. This information also allowed for the performance of validity checks to verify the robustness of our findings, acting as a sense-check for results (See Appendix D for more detail). For example, one would expect to see respondents' willingness to pay for the service to be greater at higher levels of income.

Survey testing and cognitive interviews

Prior to the distribution of the contingent valuation survey, a series of cognitive interviews were conducted to ensure the validity, relevance, and comprehensibility of the questionnaire across a diverse range of respondents. Nine cognitive interviews were conducted, with a balanced representation of academics and researchers in relevant fields and individuals from the general population. This selection of participants from both groups aimed to incorporate expert insights as well as perspectives from potential beneficiaries of the unified digital collection.

The cognitive interviews primarily focused on four key elements of the survey questionnaire:

1. Description of the good to be valued

Participants were presented with the definition of cultural heritage assets and the proposed unified digital collection encompassing such assets. Feedback was gathered on the comprehensiveness of the list of cultural heritage items proposed, as well as the clarity of the description of the unified digital collection. This input helped ensure that the survey framing achieved the intended understanding of the good to be valued.

2. Payment method

Recognising the importance of contextualising the willingness to pay question within a suitable payment framework, participants were prompted to discuss viable payment methods for expressing their valuation of the unified digital collection. This included considerations such as subscription models, donations, and taxes. Feedback on preferred payment methods informed the design of the survey questionnaire to enhance the reliability of respondents' valuations. By selecting payment mechanisms that resonated with respondents' experiences and expectations, the survey sought to create a scenario that participants could relate to, thus fostering more authentic and meaningful responses.

3. Willingness to pay

Participants were then asked to provide their maximum willingness to pay for access to the unified digital collection of cultural heritage assets. This information was used to inform the range of values presented to respondents to the three surveys that were rolled out.

4. Factors influencing willingness to pay

To gain deeper insight into why respondents value a unified digital collection, participants were asked to provide the rationale for their specified valuation. This aimed to understand the perceived benefits, features, and attributes of the digital collection that resonated with respondents, as well as potential barriers or concerns influencing their valuation decisions.

Survey recruitment and roll out

Following testing and refinement of the contingent valuation questionnaires, each survey was rolled out to target respondent groups. Roll out was conducted between November and December 2023, with our approaches to recruitment of respondents for each group summarised below. The final sample sizes for the contingent valuation study are summarised in the table below.

	General population	Academics and researchers	“Special interest” individuals
N=	7,706	283	267

General population

Respondents from the general population were recruited using the online research platform Prolific, which offers a streamlined method for accessing a diverse and representative sample of research participants, making it well-suited for survey recruitment. A small monetary incentive was provided to participants upon completion of the survey in recognition of the time and effort spent in completing the survey.

To derive robust country-specific estimates of willingness to pay, to understand the extent of any regional variations in valuations, respondents from Wales, Scotland, and Northern Ireland were oversampled relative to the makeup of the UK population. The final sample sizes for the four UK countries are summarised in the table below.

	England	Scotland	Wales	Northern Ireland
N=	4,546	1,726	957	474

Academics and researchers

A link to the survey was distributed to a database of 5,712 academics and researchers working at UK-based higher education institutions. This database was compiled from publicly available information and comprised academics and researchers (including PhD students) working in fields directly related to cultural heritage (e.g., museum, heritage, art, film, and theatre studies) as well as adjacent subjects such as in the humanities.

“Special interest” group

The questionnaire was distributed to individuals with a substantial personal interest in collections of cultural heritage assets through three main channels: (i) direct outreach through organisations operating in or related to the GLAM (galleries, libraries, archives, and museums) sector, (ii) outreach through online forums related to cultural heritage, as well as (iii) outreach through Alma Economics’ social media channels.

Data cleaning

Following closure of the surveys, the data was compiled and analysed with a data cleaning process being implemented to eliminate potentially biased or unreliable responses. A small minority of survey responses were eliminated from the analysis based on the following criteria, ensuring that only high-quality responses were included in the final analysis:

1. Thresholds for completion time

Respondents who completed the survey in two minutes or less were excluded from the final sample, with the aim of excluding respondents who completed the survey without adequately engaging with its content (this was more prevalent for the survey of the general population, where respondents were provided with monetary incentives in exchange for their participation).

2. Exclusion of “protest” responses

Consistent with guidance from HM Treasury’s Green Book on the use of Stated Preferences techniques (Pearce & Özdemiroğlu, 2002), respondents who selected only protest responses as their reasons behind unwillingness to pay were eliminated from the final sample. Specifically, respondents who exclusively selected one or more of the following protest responses were excluded:

- [For the general population survey only] I object to paying higher taxes.
- [For the general population survey only] The users of this service should pay for it directly.
- Cultural heritage organisations should pay for this from their existing funds.
- I need more information/time to answer the question.

Focus groups

Three focus groups were conducted following closure of the surveys to better understand the nuances and rationale behind participants’ responses to the survey. This approach allowed us to contextualise quantitative survey findings, understand underlying motivations, as well as to identify suggestions and concerns relevant to a future unified digital collection.

One focus group was held with each of the following groups:

- Members of the general population (consisting of both individuals with a general interest in cultural heritage and those with no clear interest in cultural heritage):** A majority of participating members of the public stated that they were personally interested in culture, museums, literature, or heritage with no participants working directly in the sector. Members of the public were recruited via community Facebook groups with coverage across all UK countries and were provided with a small monetary incentive to reflect the time and effort spent participating in the research.
- Academics and researchers:** these participants included individuals who teach or conduct research in humanities subjects (e.g., architecture, history, archaeology).
- Individuals with a “special interest” in cultural heritage:** Among individuals with a special interest in the sector, respondents outlined their varying occupations including heritage management, part-time work cataloguing historic documents, as well as conducting private historical research in retirement.

Online focus groups were conducted between January and February 2024 with a total of 23 participants across the three sessions, in addition to two written submissions of individuals who were unable to attend the sessions.

These discussions were structured along the following core topics:

- Introduction of purpose of focus group and offering opportunity for questions;
- Warm-up and introduction of participants to each other;
- Engagement with the sector by participants;
- Value of a unified digital cultural heritage collection;
- Debrief covering any remaining comments or questions.

Finally, thematic analysis of qualitative data was conducted, identifying and reporting on common themes and narratives. This includes a mapping of discussion contributions to respective themes and developing a narrative description for each theme. Substantive suggestions or concerns were then ordered based on their frequency, paying further attention to outlier responses or grievances voiced.

Limitations

There are several limitations that should be acknowledged in relation to this research, including (i) limitations specific to the circumstances of this specific study (see 1 below), and (ii) limitations inherent to the contingent valuation methodology (see 2, 3, and 4 below). These include:

1. **Valuation of a hypothetical service.** A limitation specific to this study was the hypothetical nature of the service respondents were being asked to value, an unavoidable feature given that such a service does not exist. It should be noted that respondents' eventual valuation of such a service will depend on its final scope and implementation. This study sought to mitigate this risk as far as possible by agreeing on a service description with the programme directorate and conducting cognitive interviews to ensure the description was generally well understood by respondents.
2. **Hypothetical bias with respect to payment scenario.** An individual's stated willingness to pay for a service may be inflated compared to their true valuation due to the hypothetical nature of the scenario presented in the survey. This arises mostly when a voluntary payment vehicle is used, like a donation (Lawton et al., 2022). This study attempted to mitigate this bias by presenting realistic payment scenarios – an increase in annual taxes and a monthly subscription – based on insights from the cognitive interviews and a review of precedent literature.
3. **Payment mechanism bias.** There is a risk that individuals react in a strategic way to the payment mechanisms presented in such surveys. For instance, objections to higher taxes may influence responses regardless of the actual valuation of the service. We sought to mitigate the prevalence of this bias by excluding respondents from the analysis where their rationale for a zero valuation resembled a protest response, ensuring that the final sample represented as genuine valuations as possible.
4. **Starting point (or anchoring) bias.** Contingent valuation studies run the risk of introducing an anchoring bias, whereby respondents' responses are "anchored" to the values that are presented in the questionnaire (i.e., the initial value presented with the dichotomous choice survey approach). To mitigate this bias, we employed a randomisation approach for the dichotomous choice study, randomly varying the initial value respondents were shown within a predetermined range, thus ensuring that responses were not anchored to a single value. Similarly, when utilising the payment card

approach, another form of anchoring bias may arise due to the predefined range of values presented to respondents. To address this, we defined a range of reasonable values based on insights from cognitive interviews, whilst respondents were also provided with an “other” option, allowing them to indicate willingness to pay amounts outside of the predefined range.

Contingent valuation study results

The following section provides a detailed summary of the results from the contingent valuation study.

Contingent valuation estimates for the general population

Headline estimate for Total Economic Value

Our analysis of responses from the general population survey estimates an **average willingness to pay (in terms of an increase in annual taxes) of £8.02 per person** to support the development, maintenance, and free accessibility of a unified digital collection of cultural heritage assets for the UK. By extending this result to the full UK adult population, we estimate a **Total Economic Value for the service of £425.5 million**.¹⁴

Country-specific analysis

Our analysis explored regional variation in respondents' valuation of the defined service, with estimates derived for each of England, Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland (see table below). Despite some variation across countries, average valuations were found to be relatively consistent, ranging from around £7.50 in Wales to around £9.00 in Scotland.

	England	Scotland	Wales	Northern Ireland
Willingness to pay	£7.82***	£8.81***	£7.54***	£7.96***
N=	4,546	1,726	957	474

Notes: ***significance at <1%; **significance at <5%; *significance at <10%.¹⁵

¹⁴ According to the most recent mid-year Office for National Statistics population estimates, the number of UK adults over the age of 18 was approximately 53.2 million in June 2021. See: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/populationandmigration/populationestimates/datasets/populationestimatesforukenglandandwalesscotlandandnorthernireland>

¹⁵ The econometric model employed estimates the average willingness to pay by analysing the relationship between respondents' willingness (yes/no) to pay certain amounts and these amounts themselves. The statistical significance (***, **, *) of the willingness to pay estimates emerging from this model reflects our confidence in these estimates not being by chance. A significance at <1% (***) means we are over 99% confident that the estimated willingness to pay is a true reflection of respondents' valuation, not due to random fluctuations in the data. Significance at <5% (**) and <10% (*) indicate progressively lower confidence levels (95% and 90%, respectively), but still signify that the willingness to pay estimates likely represent real willingness rather than random chance. In simpler terms, the level of significance attached to the willingness to pay estimates helps you gauge how likely it is that the amount people are willing to pay, as indicated by the study results, genuinely reflects their valuation of the service, rather than being a coincidental finding due to the particular sample of respondents who participated in the study.

Estimates based on level of interest in digital cultural heritage

Our analysis further explored if respondents' valuations of the service varied depending on their level of interest in digital collections of cultural heritage assets. Respondents were divided into two distinct groups based on their level of interest in digital collections of cultural heritage assets:

- **“No or little interest”** if they reported no engagement with digital collections in the past 12 months.
- **“General Interest”** if the individual indicated any level of engagement with digital collections in the past 12 months.

The willingness to pay estimates for these two subgroups, along with the corresponding sample sizes, are summarised in the table below:

	“No or little interest” group	“General interest” group
Willingness to pay (£)	£6.55***	£9.92***
N=	4,258	3,448

Notes: ***significance at <1%; **significance at <5%; *significance at <10%.¹⁶

This analysis reveals differences in willingness to pay between the two groups, with individuals classified under the “General Interest” category exhibiting a higher willingness to pay (£9.92) compared with those with “No or little interest” (£6.55). Despite this, it is notable that individuals with no or little demonstrable interest in digital cultural heritage collections still place a substantial valuation on the proposed service, hinting at the existence of “option” value (i.e., where individuals place a value on having the option to use the service in future) or “non-use” value (i.e., where individuals place a value on the existence of a service even if they do not currently use it).

Factors influencing a positive valuation for the service

After eliciting respondents' willingness to pay, we explored the underlying reasons driving each response. Respondents who expressed a positive willingness to pay were asked to indicate the factors that motivated their willingness to contribute financially to the proposed service. The table presents the factors influential in respondents' decisions to value the service in order of the most frequently selected:

Factors influencing positive willingness to pay	Share of respondents selecting the option
I believe this service would contribute to preserving our cultural heritage for future generations.	71%
I believe this service would make it easier for people around the world to understand UK cultural heritage.	64%
I have an interest in cultural heritage and see value in accessing digital cultural heritage assets online.	60%

¹⁶ See Footnote 15 on page 15.

I believe this service would provide me with access to assets I couldn't otherwise see.	55%
A single online platform to access the digital collections of many cultural heritage organisations would be preferable to the current situation of having to look for different collections on different organisations' webpages.	53%
I believe this service could enhance cultural experiences by enabling the development of new exhibitions.	41%
I believe this service would advance knowledge by helping researchers to explore new research questions.	40%
I believe this service would be of value for my educational or research needs.	39%
I believe this service would foster innovation by opening up new cross-collection lines of research.	34%
I believe this service would make it easier for me to access cultural heritage assets that are representative of me and my communities.	30%
Other reasons	4%

Notably, the top two reasons – preserving cultural heritage for future generations and enhancing global understanding of UK cultural heritage – relate to non-use values, emphasising the intrinsic worth individuals place on cultural heritage preservation and dissemination beyond personal consumption. Following these, the subsequent two factors reflect use value instead – the value attributed to online access to digital heritage assets, coupled with the convenience of a unified platform, underscoring the practical utility of the service to users.

Factors influencing a zero valuation for the service

Respondents who indicated they were not willing to pay any amount as an increase in annual taxes to support the unified digital cultural heritage collection (15% of the total sample), were also asked to provide reasons for their response. The table below summarises these reasons in order of prevalence.

Factors influencing a zero willingness to pay	Respondents selecting the option
I think this service is not a priority to spend taxpayers' money on.	57%
I cannot afford to pay additional taxes for this service.	49%
The benefit of this service to me is too small to be of importance.	38%
I object to paying higher taxes.	37%
I know I would not use this service.	27%
The users of this service should pay for it directly.	26%

Cultural heritage organisations should pay for this from their existing funds.	15%
I can already access digital collections through a range of other online sites.	12%
Other reasons	10%
Heritage collections are not relevant to me.	10%
I don't believe that this project could be delivered successfully.	9%
Heritage collections are not representative of me and my communities.	5%
There are other similar services around.	3%
I need more information/time to answer the question.	3%

The most frequently selected reasons, such as the view that the service is not a priority for public funding and concerns about affordability, highlight the importance of social value and individual financial constraints in shaping attitudes toward expenditure on the service. Objections to paying higher taxes and preferences for direct user payments or alternative funding mechanisms reflect broader debates surrounding government funding priorities and the allocation of resources. A portion of respondents also cited reasons related to personal relevance and scepticism about the project's feasibility.

Thematic analysis of the open-ended contributions of those 10% of respondents who selected the “other” option further highlighted that some respondents were reluctant to pay additional taxes for the digital collection for reasons such as: high existing tax burdens, scepticism about government spending efficiency, preference for in-person cultural experiences, and the belief that there are currently more critical areas in need of funding.

Contingent valuation estimates for academics and researchers

Academics and researchers were also surveyed to gather insight on their willingness to pay for the service, with these participants being presented with a scenario involving a monthly subscription fee for access to the unified digital collection, and willingness to pay being elicited using a payment card approach.

The set of values included in the payment card, notably the inclusion of three relatively high values (£100, £200 and £500), was informed by insights obtained during scoping interviews, where participants pointed out that a number of existing similar services, such as specific online archives, have rather high subscription fees.

During cognitive interviews, it was observed that while most academics and researchers expressed a positive valuation of the digital collection, many expected their universities or employing organisations to cover the subscription cost. To address this expectation and prevent an influx of false 'zero' valuations, the willingness to pay question included a note clarifying that if respondents believed their university or other employing organisation should pay on their behalf, they should specify the maximum amount they considered reasonable for them to pay for their personal access to the service.

The distribution of willingness to pay responses was as follows:

Willingness to pay option	Frequency of selection	Share of responses
£0	82	29%
£5	86	30%
£10	70	25%
£20	29	10%
£50	7	2%
£100	2	<1%
£200	0	0%
£500	3	1%
Other	4	1%

We found there to be a **mean willingness to pay for a monthly subscription amongst academics and researchers of £13.32** (£159.84 annually), with a median willingness to pay of £5 (£60 annually).

Factors influencing willingness to pay

The table below summarises the motivations behind positive willingness to pay selected by academics and researchers, ordered by prevalence.

Factors influencing positive willingness to pay	Respondents selecting the option
I have an interest in cultural heritage and see value in accessing digital cultural heritage assets online.	79%
I believe this service would be of value for my educational or research needs.	75%
I believe this service would foster innovation by opening up new cross-collection lines of research.	69%
I believe this service would advance knowledge by helping researchers to explore new research questions.	69%
I believe this service would provide me with access to assets I couldn't otherwise see.	68%
I believe this service would contribute to preserving our cultural heritage for future generations.	67%
A single online platform to access the digital collections of many cultural heritage organisations would be preferable to the current situation of having to look for different collections on different organisations' webpages.	65%

I believe this service would make it easier for people around the world to understand UK cultural heritage.	64%
I believe this service could enhance cultural experiences by enabling the development of new exhibitions.	54%
I believe this service would make it easier for me to access cultural heritage assets that are representative of me and my communities.	33%
Other	11%

Many academics and researchers placed a high value on the service improving access to digital cultural heritage assets for educational and research purposes, underscoring the critical role the service could play in academic and research-related activities. This is particularly evident in the high percentages of these individuals selecting as reasons for their positive valuation of the service options related to the perceived value of the service for educational and research needs, as well as its potential to advance knowledge through cross-disciplinary exploration and helping address new research questions. Additionally, the strong sentiment toward preserving cultural heritage for future generations highlights the commitment of many academics and researchers to safeguarding cultural legacy.

The table below presents the factors influencing the decision of the academics and researchers who were not willing to pay any amount for a unified digital collection, as indicated by respondents.

Factors influencing zero willingness to pay	Respondents selecting the option
Other	63%
I can already access digital collections through a range of other online sites.	38%
I cannot afford to pay a monthly subscription for this service.	20%
I think this service is not a priority to spend my money on.	20%
I don't believe that this project could be delivered successfully.	17%
The benefit of this service to me is too small to be of importance.	12%
I need more information/time to answer the question.	12%
I know I would not use this service.	7%
Cultural heritage organisations should pay for this from their existing funds.	7%
There are other similar services around.	5%
Heritage collections are not relevant to me.	1%
Heritage collections are not representative of me and my communities.	1%

Notably, the most frequently selected option was “Other”, highlighting the wide range of factors influencing the unwillingness to pay, as respondents provided varied reasons not captured by the predefined choices. The thematic analysis of these open-ended responses revealed a pronounced preference for treating digital cultural

heritage as a public good that should be freely accessible to everyone. The predominant sentiment among academics and researchers was that government or public funding, rather than individual subscriptions, should sustain such a service. There was a strong opposition to any model that would erect paywalls, with many expressing concerns about perpetuating inequalities and limiting access for those less financially able. The responses also called for institutional responsibility, suggesting that universities and possibly corporate sponsors should bear the cost to ensure open access. Additionally, a unified digital collection was welcomed by many in principle but deemed less realistic or desirable compared to enhancing interoperability among existing digital resources. In summary, the overarching themes were inclusivity, universal access, and the recognition of cultural heritage as a communal value that transcends economic valuation.

Among the predefined options, concerns about existing access to digital collections emerged as a prominent theme, with a significant percentage of respondents indicating that they can already access similar resources through other online platforms. This suggests that perceived redundancy or adequacy of existing services would diminish the value of the proposed service. Financial considerations also featured prominently, with a substantial proportion of academics and researchers citing lack of affordability as a deterrent, alongside doubts about the prioritisation of expenditure on such a service.

Contingent valuation estimates for the “special interest” group

As detailed in the methodology section, we conducted a dedicated survey to engage individuals with an expected vested interest in cultural heritage and gauge their willingness to pay for access to a unified digital collection. Upon completion of the data cleaning process, which involved excluding incomplete responses and implementing the data cleaning steps outlined in the methodology section, the survey reached a total sample size of 267 individuals. Unlike the general population survey, where the willingness to pay questions were framed in terms of an increase in annual taxes to ensure free accessibility to the digital collection, participants in this survey were presented with a scenario involving a monthly subscription fee for access to the unified digital collection.

The table below summarises the distribution of responses across the various values included in the payment card as options for respondents to express their willingness to pay. These values were informed by the cognitive interviews conducted prior to the survey administration.

Willingness to pay option	Frequency of selection	Share of responses
£0	121	45%
£2	42	16%
£5	60	23%
£10	35	13%
£15	4	2%
£20	2	<1%
£25	1	<1%
Other	2	<1%

Notably, a substantial share of respondents (45%) indicated a willingness to pay of £0, suggesting a significant segment of the “special interest” group may prioritise free access to digital heritage assets.

The **mean willingness to pay for a monthly subscription among the “special interest” group was £3.24** (£38.88 annually), while the median willingness to pay was £2 (£24 annually). These results suggest a willingness among individuals with a special interest in cultural heritage to contribute financially towards access to a unified digital collection. However, the substantial proportion of respondents expressing a zero willingness to pay highlights the importance of considering alternative funding models to ensure broad accessibility to these heritage assets.

Factors influencing willingness to pay

The main reasons motivating “special interest” individuals to express a positive willingness to pay for a unified digital collection are summarised in the table below, ordered by preference:

Factors influencing positive willingness to pay	Respondents selecting the option
I have an interest in cultural heritage and see value in accessing digital cultural heritage assets online.	87%
I believe this service would foster innovation by opening up new cross-collection lines of research.	78%
A single online platform to access the digital collections of many cultural heritage organisations would be preferable to the current situation of having to look for different collections on different organisations’ webpages.	77%
I believe this service would advance knowledge by helping researchers to explore new research questions.	73%
I believe this service would be of value for my educational or research needs.	72%
I believe this service would contribute to preserving our cultural heritage for future generations.	71%
I believe this service would make it easier for people around the world to understand UK cultural heritage.	65%
I believe this service would provide me with access to assets I couldn't otherwise see.	62%
I believe this service could enhance cultural experiences by enabling the development of new exhibitions.	54%
I believe this service would make it easier for me to access cultural heritage assets that are representative of me and my communities.	36%
Other	7%

These responses reveal a strong association of “special interest” individuals' valuing of the service with factors related to research, education, and cultural preservation. Nearly 90% of respondents emphasised their intrinsic interest in cultural heritage, reflecting an appreciation for the significance of digital access to heritage assets. Moreover, the desire to foster innovation and advance knowledge underscores the instrumental role such a service can play in facilitating interdisciplinary research and scholarly exploration.

The reasons why “special interest” individuals expressed a zero willingness to pay for the unified digital collection are outlined in the following table, listed in descending order of prevalence.

Factors influencing a zero willingness to pay	Respondents selecting the option
Other	61%
I can already access digital collections through a range of other online sites.	43%
I cannot afford to pay a monthly subscription for this service.	22%
I think this service is not a priority to spend my money on.	22%
I don't believe that this project could be delivered successfully.	20%
The benefit of this service to me is too small to be of importance.	17%
Cultural heritage organisations should pay for this from their existing funds.	10%
There are other similar services around.	9%
I know I would not use this service.	8%
I need more information/time to answer the question.	8%
Heritage collections are not representative of me and my communities.	2%
Heritage collections are not relevant to me.	0%

The “Other” category was the most selected option, indicating a diverse range of reasons not captured by the predefined choices. Our thematic analysis of these open-ended statements reveals a strong consensus among “special interest” individuals against a subscription-based model. These respondents commonly argued that free access to cultural heritage is a fundamental right and that imposing a subscription fee would lead to economic discrimination, denying access to those who cannot afford it. This group maintained that the government should bear the responsibility of funding and preserving cultural heritage, ensuring it remains freely available to everyone. It was stressed that cultural heritage should remain a public good and should thus be universally accessible, not restricted behind a paywall. Among the predefined choices, other factors such as the availability of alternative online resources and financial considerations emerged prominently. Additionally, concerns regarding the project's feasibility and perceived lack of personal relevance also influenced respondents' decision not to express a positive willingness to pay.

Focus group analysis

Following the conclusion of the survey analysis, participants from three focus groups were asked to outline reasons for their willingness or unwillingness to pay for the proposed service, as well as other factors influencing their responses. The insights gathered through these focus groups are summarised below.

Rationale for valuing the service

A majority of participants across all focus groups stated that they would use the service if available. Participants were then asked whether they would be willing to pay for the service and, if so, to what extent and why. Participants across all focus groups differed in whether they would be willing to pay at all for the service, and if so, how much and through which payment method. Focus group participants gave the following main reasons for valuing the service:

- **Unlocking a “democratic approach” to heritage:** It was expected that the service would make cultural heritage assets available and accessible to a wider and more diverse set of audiences. It was considered that establishing the platform would save researchers and academics time and enable resource-efficient overviews of heritage assets held by relevant institutions. Similarly, members of the special interest group discussed conducting research in their free time with little financial support and thus felt they would be aided by the availability of a central platform. Members of the public appreciated the potential for accessing heritage more flexibly, such as the ability to use the service around the clock rather than depending on restrictive opening hours. Particular emphasis was placed on increasing opportunities for access for students and groups with limited financial means.
- **Importance of accessibility of the platform:** Participants explained that even if some users paid for the service, they would expect the platform to be available to others for free. Relatedly, participants across focus groups proactively discussed the potential for the service to improve accessibility for certain groups, especially for disabled users of the platform or those living in remote rural areas.
- **The value of including “hidden assets”:** Academics as well as members of special interest groups furthermore emphasised the value of including artefacts not currently on display in museums due to space constraints or curatorial decisions. This would allow access to a wider range of material relevant to research without travelling and the associated financial and climate costs.
- **Accessing heritage in times of crisis:** Another important benefit identified was the ability to access heritage in times of crisis, with examples cited including possible future pandemics, or the viewing of art from conflict zones or territories affected by natural disasters.

Factors influencing the extent of participants’ valuation

Academics and special interest groups explained that their willingness to pay would be heavily contingent on the extent to which related digital services they currently use would be included in the new platform. Examples cited encompassed newspaper archives and online library services. Participants also raised several other questions upon which their valuation would depend, such as querying whether the novel unified platform would only include assets available on existing platforms or whether it would include additional efforts to digitise currently inaccessible heritage assets, in which case their valuation would increase. It was also questioned whether the service could be paid for on a “pay-as-you-use” basis, for example with researchers

only paying for specific segments of the platform relevant to their work. A majority of participating members of the public also asked whether an app would be available, given this would influence their valuation of the platform. Other respondents specified that while they were willing to pay for the period of platform development as a specified purpose, they would not be willing to pay for ongoing use in future years once established.

Participants furthermore explained that their willingness or unwillingness to pay for the proposed service would be contingent on the payment mechanism employed. Given concerns over the ability of universities and research institutes to afford paying a journal-type subscription fee on behalf of researchers, it was instead preferred by academics and members of special interest groups that the service be funded via a general tax. Another group of participants suggested a hybrid model – this could partly be funded through taxation, as well as donations and contributions from wealthier institutions through a tiered system or even advertisements on the platform. It was suggested by some that any payment type should be adjusted by income level.

Rationale for not valuing the service

Respondents who stated that they would not be willing to pay for the service gave several reasons for their decision. Most frequently, participants discussed the following arguments:

- **Heritage should be free and accessible to everyone:** Many of these participants viewed that heritage assets should remain freely accessible and be maintained as a core educational resource across the UK. Participants often thought that inclusivity and accessibility of knowledge should not be treated as having a monetary value and instead should be viewed as having an inherent yet intangible value. Some participating academics and affiliated researchers accepted that their institutions could pay a subscription-type service fee; however, concerns were raised that universities were currently experiencing challenging budget cuts and a wider lack of funding. Universities were therefore seen as possibly unable or unwilling to pay for a subscription fee to the novel platform which would lead to unequal and unfair access. In consequence, some participants argued against a subscription-based payment model for public sector institutions such as universities.
- **The majority of assets are already available on other free platforms:** It was also commonly explained that a majority of assets likely to be included in the proposed service were already freely available elsewhere, leading participants to question why they should pay for a service which already existed, even if across several different websites.
- **Funding should be utilised for digitisation of undocumented materials instead:** A further group of participants expressed a preference to spend the allocated funding on the digitisation of thus far undocumented materials instead. It was explained that sufficient access to existing digital cultural heritage was already achieved but new material would need to be made “discoverable”, either as part of the new or existing platforms.
- **Maintaining free access to the platform catalogue:** Finally, academics and special interest groups alike emphasised that the catalogue of any such platform should never be put behind a paywall, even if the actual engagement with assets was subject to a fee. Access to online catalogues was seen as enabling researchers and members of the public to identify which assets would be held in which physical locations and to gain an overview of what could be accessed through the unified digital platform before paying a subscription-type access fee.

Participants' suggestions for features

When discussing their willingness to pay for the service, participants raised a number of suggestions for features or desired functionality of the future digital collection. Such suggestions varied widely by the type of user and across focus groups.

- **Features to promote accessibility of the digital collection:** All three focus groups made a range of suggestions of how to support accessibility, for example through the adaptability for screen readers, providing textual descriptions of visual objects, and offering translations into other commonly spoken languages. Members of the public emphasised in particular that providing multiple access points (desktop and apps, including possible offline functionality) would be a vital contributor to the value of the service. It was viewed that a focus should be placed on early and consistent user testing during the iterative platform development, avoiding risks such as overwhelming users with the information displayed or unintuitive platform navigation. Looking into the future, participants emphasised that the platform should be made as widely available as possible, for example by being included on public library computers across the UK and in schools, given that staff members could support users in those physical spaces.
- **Ensuring the flexible searchability of the platform:** Academics, researchers, and members of the public alike highlighted that being able to locate and search for specific items in the online catalogue was crucial. Participants advocated for the possibility of being able to investigate certain “tags” – for example, specific artists or styles – leading them directly to a selection of related assets.
- **Enabling the possibility of comparing and contrasting objects:** According to academics and researchers, this would meaningfully contribute to their work, for example, allowing them to view assets side-by-side which are physically located in different parts of the country. A related suggested functional feature mentioned was the ability to line assets up chronologically or by another consistent criterion, allowing users to sort and organise heritage assets for research purposes.
- **Considering further creative engagement tools:** Researchers queried the formats in which assets could be viewed, citing examples such as videos of artefacts or turning artefacts around to assess them from different angles. Additional suggestions included “gamified elements”, quizzes, as well as live events and webinars or virtual tours through exhibitions.

Concerns raised around the implementation of the platform

Participants across the three focus groups raised a number of concerns and risks associated with the development of a unified digital collection. Issues were raised primarily around the following themes:

- **Reliability of a single unified digital platform:** Academics, researchers, and members of special interest groups referenced recent incidents such as the British Library’s system being hacked and thus inaccessible to users for a prolonged period. Participants also emphasised a wider lack of trust in the reliability and security of existing digital platforms and catalogues.
- **Challenges with defining “heritage”:** Participants raised concerns over how “heritage” would be defined for the purposes of the service and who would get to decide on such definitions, which would impact the scope of assets that would be integrated into the service. Specifically, participants raised

questions over who would control platform finances and data security, and how decisions would be made when updating the platform with new content or cataloguing information. Participating academics and members of special interest groups alike cautioned that any definition of heritage should also include historical sites and monuments, as well as maintain a clear distinction between the cultural meaning and reference to physical heritage assets.

- **Approaching contested or retraumatising heritage:** Further questions and concerns were raised about potentially contested or retraumatising heritage being included and displayed online. Across all focus groups, the importance of trigger warnings and content restrictions for groups (e.g. below 18 years old) was raised, with some arguing that selected assets should be reserved for researchers with special permission only.
- **Unintended consequences for existing digital collections:** Some participants raised concerns that existing digital collections, especially of smaller size, would be impacted by the development of a new unified digital platform. These participants shared their view that fewer online visits to these services could decrease the commercial potential of such services.
- **Balanced integration of existing sources:** Further concerns raised by respondents included the need to achieve a balance between smaller, larger, and private collections if their content was to be integrated into the newly established platform. It was viewed that the cataloguing of content across many different institutions could create challenges, for example, if existing collections and assets were catalogued differently or if different terminology was used. There could therefore be potential challenges around the time and resources necessary to integrate a range of existing digital materials.

Appendix A: Literature review of relevant studies

There is a small but growing body of literature focusing on the application of contingent valuation techniques within the cultural heritage sector, encompassing studies conducted in the UK and internationally. These studies have explored the economic valuation of access to, and preservation of, various heritage assets such as castles, historic towns, high streets, and cathedrals. Early examples include Willis (1994), who used contingent valuation to estimate the maximum individuals would be willing to pay for access to Durham Cathedral, and A. Powe & Willis (1996), who applied contingent valuation to determine the benefits received by visitors to Warkworth Castle in Northumbria. Similarly, Garrod et al. (1996) utilised contingent valuation to investigate public preferences for the renovation of historic buildings in the Grainger Town area of Newcastle upon Tyne. Pollicino & Maddison (2002) employed contingent valuation to evaluate the gross benefits arising from a hypothetical cleaning program at Lincoln Cathedral, aimed at repairing damages caused by air pollution. Özdemiroğlu et al. (2014) applied contingent valuation to estimate the benefits of maintaining Castle Acre Priory and Walmer Castle and Gardens, specifically measuring individuals' willingness to pay to protect the site over and above their current contributions through entrance fees, membership fees, or public taxes. Lawton et al. (2018) utilised contingent valuation to estimate the value of four historic cities and their cathedrals (Canterbury, York, Lincoln, and Winchester), considering a hypothetical scenario of a threat from climate change and a shortfall in funding. Lawton et al. (2021) revealed local heritage values for historic high streets and historic civic buildings from local residents in eight English cities, including Bolton, Huddersfield, Hull, Bristol, Exeter, Lincoln, Norwich, and York.

The application of contingent valuation extends to the GLAM (galleries, libraries, archives, and museums) sector as well. Santagata & Signorello (2000) conducted a contingent valuation study to measure the non-use value of a network of cultural venues making up the Napoli Musei Aperti in Naples, Italy, under a hypothetical scenario where public funds would be withdrawn. Sanz et al. (2003) used contingent valuation to elicit willingness to pay for the preservation and maintenance of the National Museum of Sculpture in Valladolid, Spain. Pung et al. (2004) estimated the impact of the British Library on the UK economy through contingent valuation in a hypothetical scenario of ceased government funding. Stevenson (2013) explored the benefits provided to users of the National Galleries of Scotland, as well as the broader societal and economic benefits valued by citizens through a contingent valuation study. Bakhshi et al. (2015) combined contingent valuation and wellbeing valuation to uncover the value of key non-market services provided by the Natural History Museum and Tate Liverpool. Fujiwara et al. (2018) sought to understand the economic value that four specific museums provide to both visitors and non-visitors. Lawton et al. (2021) provided monetary estimates of the benefits that regional art galleries offer to visitors and the local population in England, using four galleries as case studies. Fujiwara et al. (2022) estimated the value of engagement in library services through a contingent valuation study of a large sample of library users and non-users.

The literature specifically addressing digital cultural heritage assets through contingent valuation is notably limited, reflecting the challenges in applying these techniques to experiences that are novel to consumers and the inherent difficulty in valuing digital content that is often free to access. To date, only two examples have been identified. Lawton et al. (2022) conducted a contingent valuation study to estimate the willingness to pay for a free online film archive portal, Britain on Film, asking respondents about their willingness to pay for the actual service and the broader conservation work and research of archive film behind the service. Three online surveys elicited willingness to pay values from first-time users, existing users, and non-users. Users were willing to pay an average hypothetical subscription of £38.52 per annum. Non-users were instead asked their

willingness to pay a hypothetical annual donation to maintain free public access to the portal, indicating an average willingness to pay of £4.68 per annum. Arber et al. (2023) assessed individuals' willingness to pay for accessing the digital offer of four museums and art galleries in England, defining 'digital offer' as the free-to-access online content provided by these institutions. Results indicate an average willingness to pay for a monthly subscription to continue accessing the digital offer ranging from £3.27 to £4.93 per person across the four museums or galleries.

Appendix B: Willingness to pay in theory

As detailed in the methodology section, two different approaches were employed to elicit willingness to pay from different respondent groups: the double-bounded dichotomous choice (DBDC) method to analyse responses to the general population survey, and the payment card approach for academics and researchers, and the special interest group. The theoretical underpinning for generating willingness to pay results using these two approaches is summarised below.

Double-bounded dichotomous choice

As part of the questionnaire, these respondents were asked two consecutive willingness to pay questions:

- Respondents were first presented with a question asking if they were willing to pay a given amount to support the development, maintenance, and free accessibility of the unified digital collection described in the survey. The offered amount was randomised to each respondent from a set of predetermined values.
- If respondents answered affirmatively, a second identical question was posed with double the initial amount; if, instead, they declined, the second question was asked with half the initial amount.

A detailed explanation of the theoretical underpinnings of the DBDC model is summarised in Lopez-Feldman (2012). Respondents can be classified into four categories based on their answers to the two willingness to pay questions: yes-yes, yes-no, no-yes, and no-no. Each combination of responses provides different insights into the respondent's willingness to pay. For instance, a yes-no response indicates that the respondent's willingness to pay lies between the first and second amounts offered.

The econometric estimation using the DBDC model involves estimating the probability of each combination of responses occurring. The probability of observing each combination of responses is modelled based on the relationship between respondents' answers and the proposed payment amounts. Statistical assumptions are made about the distribution of respondents' willingness to pay. In other words, the model assumes that people's willingness to pay varies in a predictable way, based on known factors (like their income or age) whilst some random variation cannot be directly observed.

By analysing the distribution of responses across the entire sample, the model estimates the parameters that describe the overall distribution of willingness to pay across the sample. The estimated parameters are those that maximise the likelihood of observing the actual combination of answers in the sample. These parameters are then used to calculate the willingness to pay for the whole sample.

Payment card

In the surveys targeting academics and researchers, and the “special interest” group, willingness to pay was elicited using a payment card approach. Respondents were presented with a list of monetary values – including zero, and an open-ended “other” option – and asked to indicate their maximum willingness to pay, as a monthly subscription, for access to the unified digital collection.

When analysing the results, each observation is associated with a single value representing the respondent's maximum willingness to pay, therefore the average willingness to pay is calculated as the nonparametric mean of all individual willingness to pay values in the sample. Calculating the mean willingness to pay is good practice in contingent valuation studies (Vaughan et al., 2000), though the median is also calculated to provide additional insights into the distribution of individual willingness to pay across the two samples.

Appendix C: Distribution of responses to the double-bounded dichotomous choice survey

The table below provides an overview of the distribution of responses in relation to the amounts offered to survey participants from the general population in the first willingness to pay question. Each respondent was randomly assigned a value of £1, £2, £4 or £8 as an increase in annual taxes to support the development and maintenance of, and free accessibility to, the unified digital collection. The second and third columns present the number of respondents answering No or Yes to the first question, whereas the following four columns show the number of respondents for each of the four combinations of responses to the two consecutive willingness to pay questions. The last column presents the total number of respondents being randomly offered each of the four initial amounts, as well as the total sample size, composed of 7,706 individuals.

First amount	Response to first amount		Combination of responses to first and second amounts				Total
	No	Yes	No-No	No-Yes	Yes-No	Yes-Yes	
£1	382	1513	249	133	266	1,247	1,895
£2	516	1474	325	191	392	1,082	1,990
£4	582	1354	319	263	529	825	1,936
£8	730	1155	420	310	532	623	1,885
Total	2,210	5,496	1,313	897	1,719	3,777	7,706

From the distribution of responses to the first question, we observe that respondents who answered “Yes” outnumbered those who answered “No” across all initial amounts offered. As expected, the number of respondents who declined increased as the initial amount offered increased, while the opposite trend was observed for affirmative responses, suggesting an intuitive sensitivity to price variations among respondents.

This data also revealed a high proportion of respondents who expressed a positive willingness to pay. A substantial majority, 83% of the sample, replied “Yes” to at least one of the two questions. This finding underscores the perceived value and importance attributed to a unified digital collection, reflecting a significant level of public interest and support for its development and accessibility.

Appendix D: Validity testing in the general population survey

Predictors of willingness to pay

To assess the robustness of the contingent valuation study findings, we conducted a process of validity testing, consistent with established methodologies and HM Treasury Green Book guidance (Pearce & Özdemiroğlu, 2002), which involved examining the association between willingness to pay for the unified digital collection and various socio-demographic, behavioural, and attitudinal factors. Specifically, we included a number of dummy variables built on these factors as controls in the DBDC model. By doing so, we aimed to assess whether willingness to pay is influenced by factors that align with theoretical expectations, thus providing additional confidence in the reliability and validity of our willingness to pay estimates. The results of this validity check are summarised in the table below.

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error
Gender (female)	-0.689***	0.198
Age (under 35)	-0.318	0.200
Income (under £25,000)	-0.718***	0.206
Education (tertiary)	0.546***	0.208
Ethnicity (non-white)	-1.835***	0.305
Visit to collection (twice in the past year or less)	-0.377*	0.219
Digital engagement (never in the past year)	-0.161	0.216
Member of heritage organisations	0.950***	0.300
Agreement with 1 st statement	1.644***	0.301
Agreement with 2 nd statement	1.177***	0.273
Agreement with 3 rd statement	-0.872***	0.208
Agreement with 4 th statement	1.844***	0.215
Agreement with 5 th statement	1.074***	0.243
Agreement with 6 th statement	-1.247*	0.643
Agreement with 7 th statement	0.798***	0.241
Agreement with 8 th statement	2.702***	0.237
Frequency of hypothetical use (at least once a month)	3.155***	0.240

Notes: ***significance at <1%; **significance at <5%; *significance at <10%.¹⁷

The negative coefficient (-0.689***) associated with gender indicates that being female is significantly correlated with a lower willingness to pay compared to not being female. On average, female respondents exhibit a willingness to pay that is approximately £0.69 lower, highlighting a relative gender disparity in the valuation of a unified digital collection. Additionally, while the coefficient for ages under 35 (-0.318) suggests a slightly lower willingness to pay compared to older age groups, this relationship is not statistically significant, indicating that age may have limited influence on individuals' valuation. Conversely, the negative coefficient (-0.718***) for income below £25,000 annually underscores the impact of economic factors on willingness to pay. Individuals with lower income levels demonstrate a significantly lower willingness to pay, reflecting the financial constraints that may limit their ability to allocate funds towards cultural expenditures.

The positive coefficient (0.546***) associated with tertiary education highlights the positive relationship between educational attainment and willingness to pay. Respondents with tertiary education exhibit a higher valuation, reflecting their heightened cultural engagement and greater appreciation for cultural heritage initiatives. The negative coefficient (-1.835***) for non-white ethnicity indicates a significant disparity in willingness to pay based on ethnic background. Individuals from non-white ethnic backgrounds demonstrate a significantly lower willingness to pay compared to their white counterparts, suggesting disparities in cultural engagement and preferences that warrant further investigation.

The negative coefficients associated with visits to collections (-0.377*) suggests that individuals who reported visiting GLAMs less frequently in the past year demonstrate a lower willingness to pay. This finding aligns with expectations, as individuals who engage less frequently with physical cultural institutions may perceive less value in digital initiatives aimed at enhancing access to their collections. Similarly, the negative coefficient (-0.161) associated with digital engagement indicates that individuals who reported never engaging with cultural heritage in digital form over the past year exhibit a lower willingness to pay. Conversely, the positive coefficient (0.950***) for membership in heritage organisations highlights the significant impact of organisational affiliation on individuals' willingness to pay. Overall, the three coefficients associated with behavioural factors align with theoretical expectations, supporting the validity of our results.

The coefficients associated with agreement with statements reflecting attitudes toward cultural heritage provide further validation of our willingness to pay results, as the signs of these coefficients align with expectations. Individuals who expressed agreement or strong agreement with positively worded statements (1st, 2nd, 4th, 5th, 7th, and 8th) affirming the importance of preserving cultural heritage collections and supporting cultural heritage organisations exhibit higher willingness to pay, as indicated by the positive coefficients. These statements likely resonate with individuals who value cultural heritage and recognise its significance in society, leading to a greater willingness to contribute financially to initiatives aimed at preserving and promoting cultural heritage assets. Conversely, the negative coefficients associated with agreement with negatively worded statements (3rd and 6th), such as the belief that there are more valuable pursuits than visiting cultural

¹⁷ The significance levels accompanying the coefficients in this table reflect the strength of the statistical association between each factor and the willingness to pay across the sample. Specifically, a significance level of less than 1% (***) indicates that we are 99% confident the observed association between a particular factor and willingness to pay is not due to random chance but represents a real pattern within our sample. Levels of significance at less than 5% (**) and less than 10% (*) represent progressively lower levels of confidence – at 95% and 90% respectively – but still indicate that the associations observed are likely to be more than coincidental findings within our sample.

heritage collections or the perception that cultural heritage collections have limited relevance in contemporary society, are consistent with lower willingness to pay among individuals who hold such views.

Finally, individuals who indicated a higher likelihood of hypothetical regular use (at least once a month) of the unified digital collection exhibit significantly higher willingness to pay, as evidenced by the positive coefficient (3.155***), which is the highest in magnitude among all the coefficients that emerged from the model. This finding aligns with expectations, suggesting that individuals who anticipate frequent hypothetical utilisation of the digital collection place greater value on its accessibility and benefits.

In summary, these findings highlight the complex interplay of socio-demographic, attitudinal, and behavioural factors in shaping individuals' valuation of cultural heritage initiatives. The consistent alignment of coefficients with theoretical expectations, alongside the high prevalence of statistical significance, underscores the robustness and validity of our results.

Open-ended follow-up willingness to pay question

As an additional step to validate the robustness of the contingent valuation findings, we cross-referenced the results from the two consecutive DBDC questions with the results from an open-ended question where respondents were asked to specify the precise amount they were willing to contribute annually through increased taxes. For respondents who answered “Yes” to at least one of the DBDC questions, this step provided an opportunity to directly express their willingness to pay. Conversely, for those who answered “No” to both questions, we first inquired if they were willing to contribute any amount, no matter how small. If affirmative, respondents were asked to indicate their maximum willingness to pay; otherwise, they were coded as zero.

Upon collecting these open-ended responses, we performed a data-cleaning process to ensure consistency with the earlier DBDC responses. Responses falling outside the range indicated in the DBDC questions were considered inconsistent and subsequently excluded from the analysis. This step helped mitigate potential biases arising from respondents' misinterpretation of the question.

The analysis of the open-ended responses yielded a mean willingness to pay of £9.39, slightly exceeding the willingness to pay elicited through the DBDC model (£8.02). This discrepancy can be attributed to a small proportion of outliers, with more than 5% of respondents indicating values of £30 or higher. However, the median willingness to pay was £5, indicating that at least half of the respondents expressed a willingness to pay of £5 or less annually and reflecting the presence of lower-valued responses, including almost 15% of the sample unwilling to pay any amount.

Appendix E: Summary statistics

Socio-demographic characteristics

The table below summarises the socio-demographic characteristics of respondents across the three surveys.

Question	Category	General population	“Special interest” group	Academics and researchers
Sex	Female	58%	62%	49%
	Male	42%	29%	44%
	Other	<1%	2%	1%
Age	16 – 25	10%	2%	1%
	26 – 35	30%	16%	12%
	36 – 45	26%	25%	28%
	46 – 55	17%	26%	26%
	56 – 65	11%	15%	22%
	66+	5%	11%	5%
Ethnicity	Asian, Asian Welsh, or Asian British	5%	1%	4%
	Black, Black Welsh, Black British, Caribbean or African	3%	-	2%
	Mixed or multiple ethnic groups	2%	2%	5%
	Other ethnic group	1%	2%	14%
	White	88%	88%	78%
Education	No formal education	<1%	-	-
	Primary/elementary school	<1%	-	-
	Secondary/high school	14%	<1%	-
	Vocational/technical training	8%	-	-
	College/university (without a degree)	15%	4%	-
	Bachelor’s degree	40%	17%	3%
	Master’s degree	18%	48%	9%

	Doctorate/PhD	3%	26%	87%
Income	Under £25,000	35%	17%	5%
	£25,000 to £50,000	46%	51%	36%
	Over £50,000	14%	21%	50%
Residence	Scotland	22%	22%	24%
	Wales	12%	4%	15%
	Northern Ireland	6%	<1%	<1%
	England – London	9%	23%	11%
	England – North East	3%	2%	9%
	England – North West	8%	6%	5%
	England – Yorkshire and the Humber	7%	6%	4%
	England – East Midlands	5%	4%	4%
	England – West Midlands	6%	4%	6%
	England – South East	10%	11%	9%
	England – South West	7%	6%	4%
	England – East of England	5%	6%	7%
	Outside of the UK	<1%	4%	2%

Behaviours and attitudes towards cultural heritage

The table below summarises the answers to the behavioural questions across the three surveys.

Question	Category	General population	“Special interest” group	Academics and researchers
Visits to GLAMs	At least once a week	2%	29%	17%
	Less often than once a week but at least once a month	9%	35%	42%
	Less often than once a month but at least 3 or 4 times a year	31%	28%	32%
	Twice in the past 12 months	22%	6%	7%
	Once in the past 12 months	18%	2%	2%
	Not at all in the past 12 months	18%	1%	1%

Engagement with digital collections	At least once a week	1%	43%	32%
	Less often than once a week but at least once a month	4%	27%	24%
	Less often than once a month but at least 3 or 4 times a year	12%	16%	20%
	Twice in the past 12 months	10%	6%	8%
	Once in the past 12 months	17%	3%	7%
	Not at all in the past 12 months	55%	5%	8%
Membership to heritage organisations	Yes	14%	79%	51%
	No	86%	21%	49%

The table below summarises the answers to the attitudinal questions across the three surveys.

Question	Category	General population	"Special interest" group	Academics and researchers
Preserving cultural heritage collections for the appreciation of current and future generations is important to me.	Strongly disagree	1%	1%	2%
	Disagree	4%	-	<1%
	Neither agree nor disagree	12%	-	1%
	Agree	56%	9%	14%
	Strongly agree	28%	90%	82%
Being able to visit or access cultural heritage collections enriches my life.	Strongly disagree	1%	1%	2%
	Disagree	5%	-	-
	Neither agree nor disagree	16%	1%	<1%
	Agree	52%	18%	19%
	Strongly agree	27%	80%	79%
When it comes to spending my time and money, there are things I find more valuable than visiting cultural heritage collections.	Strongly disagree	2%	6%	7%
	Disagree	11%	27%	22%
	Neither agree nor disagree	38%	41%	42%
	Agree	37%	21%	23%
	Strongly agree	13%	6%	6%

Supporting cultural heritage organisations and the preservation of cultural heritage collections should be a priority in government budget allocations.	Strongly disagree	2%	1%	1%
	Disagree	12%	2%	1%
	Neither agree nor disagree	30%	6%	12%
	Agree	44%	33%	31%
	Strongly agree	12%	58%	55%
I value the role of cultural heritage collections in promoting social cohesion and a sense of belonging.	Strongly disagree	1%	1%	2%
	Disagree	6%	3%	3%
	Neither agree nor disagree	21%	7%	13%
	Agree	57%	43%	35%
	Strongly agree	15%	46%	46%
Cultural heritage collections have little relevance to the society we live in today.	Strongly disagree	27%	69%	66%
	Disagree	50%	27%	28%
	Neither agree nor disagree	12%	3%	3%
	Agree	9%	2%	1%
	Strongly agree	2%	<1%	2%
I consider cultural heritage institutions and their collections as important contributors to the overall wellbeing of communities.	Strongly disagree	1%	<1%	1%
	Disagree	8%	1%	1%
	Neither agree nor disagree	22%	6%	8%
	Agree	56%	46%	39%
	Strongly agree	13%	47%	52%
There is value in being able to engage with cultural heritage assets in digital form.	Strongly disagree	1%	1%	1%
	Disagree	4%	2%	1%
	Neither agree nor disagree	19%	3%	5%
	Agree	58%	40%	38%
	Strongly agree	18%	55%	55%

Appendix F: Survey questionnaire

Introduction and terms of participation

In this survey, you will be asked questions about your experience with, and attitudes towards:

1. the UK's cultural heritage,
2. a future unified digital collection of cultural heritage assets for the UK, and
3. the factors that shape your opinions on the above.

Towards the end of the survey, we will ask for information on your personal characteristics and circumstances to understand how views vary across different segments of the UK's population.

The survey is expected to take 6 minutes or less to complete.

Your participation in this survey will remain confidential, meaning that your responses will not be linked to your identity. Any data that you provide will be stored safely in the Alma Economics secure servers for a period of 12 months and will not be shared with other parties.

[General population survey only] In return for your participation, you will receive a payment of £[X]. This will be granted through Prolific within 21 days following your completion of the study. Please note that if you choose to withdraw from the research, you will no longer be eligible for an incentive payment.

If you have any questions or concerns regarding your participation in the survey, please reach out to our team's research lead Rob Dufield at rob.dufield@almaeconomics.com.

Informed consent

1. I have read and understood the terms of participation as these are outlined above, and I agree to proceed with taking the survey. [Mandatory – Yes]

Behavioural and attitudinal questions

The UK has a wide range of cultural heritage assets, held as part of cultural heritage collections, examples of which include:

- Works of art, including paintings, sculptures, photographs and contemporary artworks.
- Artifacts, such as tools, jewellery, ceramics, clothing and other items of historical significance.
- Books, manuscripts and maps.
- Other archive materials, including film and television footage, music and audio recordings, newspapers and magazines.
- Digital born assets, such as digital photographs and videos, digital audio recordings and digital artworks.

2. How often in the past 12 months you have visited museums, galleries, libraries, or archives? [Single choice - At least once a week / Less often than once a week but at least once a month / Less often than once a month but at least 3 or 4 times a year / Twice in the last 12 months / Once in the last 12 months / Never]
3. How often in the past 12 months you have engaged with digital collections of cultural heritage assets – for example, by exploring a virtual exhibition or accessing a digital archive? [Single choice - At least once a week / Less often than once a week but at least once a month / Less often than once a month but at least 3 or 4 times a year / Twice in the last 12 months / Once in the last 12 months / Never]
4. Are you a member of any cultural heritage organisations? [Single choice – Yes / No]

The following questions will ask for your views and attitudes towards culture and heritage in the UK.

5. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?
 - a. Preserving cultural heritage collections for the appreciation of current and future generations is important to me. [Single choice - Strongly agree / Agree / Neutral / Disagree / Strongly disagree]
 - b. Being able to visit or access cultural heritage collections enriches my life. [Single choice - Strongly agree / Agree / Neutral / Disagree / Strongly disagree]
 - c. When it comes to spending my time and money, there are things I find more valuable than visiting cultural heritage collections. [Single choice - Strongly agree / Agree / Neutral / Disagree / Strongly disagree]
 - d. Supporting cultural heritage organisations and the preservation of cultural heritage collections should be a priority in government budget allocations. [Single choice - Strongly agree / Agree / Neutral / Disagree / Strongly disagree]
 - e. I value the role of cultural heritage collections in promoting social cohesion and a sense of belonging. [Single choice - Strongly agree / Agree / Neutral / Disagree / Strongly disagree]
 - f. Cultural heritage collections have little relevance to the society we live in today. [Single choice - Strongly agree / Agree / Neutral / Disagree / Strongly disagree]
 - g. I consider cultural heritage institutions and their collections as important contributors to the overall wellbeing of communities. [Single choice - Strongly agree / Agree / Neutral / Disagree / Strongly disagree]
 - h. There is value in being able to engage with cultural heritage assets in digital form. [Single choice - Strongly agree / Agree / Neutral / Disagree / Strongly disagree]

Description of the service

Please read the following section carefully before proceeding with the survey.

The UK has a wide range of cultural heritage assets, held as part of cultural heritage collections, examples of which include:

- Works of art, including paintings, sculptures, photographs, and contemporary artworks.
- Artifacts, such as tools, jewellery, ceramics, clothing, and other items of historical significance.
- Books, manuscripts, and maps.
- Other archive materials, including film and television footage, music and audio recordings, newspapers, and magazines.
- Digital born assets, such as digital photographs and videos, digital audio recordings and digital artworks.

These cultural heritage assets are held as part of the collections of museums, galleries, libraries, and archives. Many of these institutions provide some form of digital access to their collections. Nevertheless, these digital resources are spread across a large number of webpages maintained by their respective institutions.

This survey's objective is to understand the value of making available on a single online platform a combined digital collection held by museums, galleries, libraries, and archives across the UK. These collections comprise of digitised versions of physical assets – consisting of photos, videos, audio or 3D reproductions – as well as digital born assets, accompanied by information that describes the context and key characteristics of each of these assets.

This service would be presented in a user-friendly online experience that, harnessing the latest technological innovations, would allow users to seamlessly explore a large amount of assets from many digital cultural heritage collections through a single interface. These collections could include those of the largest and most renowned UK cultural heritage institutions, as well as those of smaller, more local organisations.

This service would be developed through a publicly funded investment programme, using digital technology to create a unified national collection of cultural heritage assets from the UK's museums, libraries, galleries, and archives.

Hypothetical use question

6. **[General population survey only]** If this service existed, and was free and easily accessible, how often do you think you would be likely to use it? [Single choice - At least once a week / Less often than once a week but at least once a month / Less often than once a month but at least 3 or 4 times a year / Twice a year / Once a year / Less often than once a year / Not at all]

Willingness to pay questions

General population survey

For this unified digital collection of cultural heritage assets to be fully developed, made accessible to users, and maintained over the years, a steady funding stream is needed. A viable approach for achieving this involves the adoption of a taxation-based model, wherein the cost of developing and maintaining the service is collectively shouldered by all UK taxpayers, ensuring free access to the service for all.

7. Would you be willing to pay an additional [£1 / £2 / £4 / £8] in annual taxes to support the development, maintenance, and free accessibility to this service? [Single choice – Yes/No]
8. [If Yes to question 7] Would you instead be willing to pay an additional [£2 / £4 / £8 / £16] in annual taxes to support the development, maintenance and free accessibility to this service? [Single choice – Yes/No]
9. [If No to question 7] Would you instead be willing to pay an additional [£0.5 / £1 / £2 / £4] in annual taxes to support the development, maintenance and free accessibility to this service? [Single choice – Yes/No]
10. [If No to both question 7 and 9] Would you be willing to pay any amount, even if very small, as additional annual taxes to support the development, maintenance and free accessibility to this service? [Single choice – Yes/No]
11. [If Yes to at least one of questions 7, 8, 9, or 10] Could you please indicate what is the highest increase in annual taxes you would be willing to pay to support the development, maintenance and free accessibility to this service? Please provide your response as a numeric value in pounds, with no £ symbol or additional words. [Open-ended question]

“Special interest” survey only

For this unified digital collection of cultural heritage assets to be fully developed, made accessible to users, and maintained over the years, a steady funding stream is needed. A viable approach for achieving this involves the adoption of a subscription model, offering subscribers access to the service against a monthly payment.

12. By considering the list of amounts below, what is the maximum you would be willing to pay, as a monthly subscription, to have access to this service? [Single choice - £0 / £2 / £5 / £10 / £15 / £20 / £25 / Other (please specify)]

Academics/researchers survey

For this unified digital collection of cultural heritage assets to be fully developed, made accessible to users, and maintained over the years, a steady funding stream is needed. A viable approach for achieving this involves the adoption of a subscription model, offering subscribers access to the service against a monthly payment.

13. By considering the list of amounts below, what is the maximum you would be willing to pay, as a monthly subscription, to have access to this service? [Single choice - £0 / £5 / £10 / £20 / £50 / £100 / £200 / £500 / Other (please specify)]

Note: we understand that many academics and researchers would expect their university or other employing organisation to cover the subscription cost. However, we are interested in gauging your individual valuation for personal access. In case you believe your university or other employing organisation should pay on your behalf, please specify the maximum amount you would find reasonable for granting you, as an individual user, access to this service.

Rationale for willingness to pay

[If No to question 10, or £0 to question 12 or 13] The following question seeks to understand the rationale for your unwillingness to pay for a unified digital cultural heritage collection.

14. Which factors explain your unwillingness to pay for this service? [Select all that apply]

- I cannot afford to pay a monthly subscription for this service.
- The benefit of this service to me is too small to be of importance.
- I think this service is not a priority to spend my money on.
- I know I would not use this service.
- Heritage collections are not relevant to me.
- Heritage collections are not representative of me and my communities.
- There are other similar services around.
- I can already access digital collections through a range of other online sites.
- I don't believe that this project could be delivered successfully.
- Cultural heritage organisations should pay for this from their existing funds.
- I need more information/time to answer the question.
- Other (please specify)

[Otherwise] The following question seeks to understand the rationale for your unwillingness to pay for a unified digital cultural heritage collection.

15. Which factors explain your willingness to pay for this service? [Select all that apply]

- I have an interest in cultural heritage and see value in accessing digital cultural heritage assets online.
- A single online platform to access the digital collections of many cultural heritage organisations would be preferable to the current situation of having to look for different collections on different organisations webpages.
- I believe this service would provide me with access to assets I couldn't otherwise see.
- I believe this service would be of value for my educational or research needs.
- I believe this service would make it easier for me to access cultural heritage assets that are representative of me and my communities.
- I believe this service would contribute to preserving our cultural heritage for future generations.
- I believe this service could enhance cultural experiences by enabling the development of new exhibitions.
- I believe this service would foster innovation by opening up new cross-collection lines of research.

- I believe this service would advance knowledge by helping researchers to explore new research questions.
- I believe this service would make it easier for people around the world to understand UK cultural heritage.
- Other (please specify)

Socio-demographic characteristics

16. Which of the following best describes your current region of residence? [Single choice]

- Scotland
- Wales
- Northern Ireland
- England - London
- England - North East
- England - North West
- England - Yorkshire
- England - East Midlands
- England - West Midlands
- England - South East
- England - East of England
- England - South West
- Outside of the UK
- I don't know

17. Which of the following best describes your sex? [Single choice]

- Female
- Male
- Prefer not to answer
- Other (please enter the term you use to describe your sex)

18. What is your current age?

- 16 – 25
- 26 – 35
- 36 – 45
- 46 – 55

- 56 – 65
- 66+
- Prefer not to answer

19. Which of the following best describes your ethnic background? [Single choice]

- White
- Mixed or multiple ethnic groups
- Asian, Asian Welsh, or Asian British
- Black, Black Welsh, Black British, Caribbean or African
- Other ethnic group
- Prefer not to answer

20. Which of the following best represent your annual income before taxes? [Single choice]

- Under £25,000
- Between £25,000 and £50,000
- Over £50,000
- I don't know
- Prefer not to answer

21. Which of the following best represent the highest level of education you have completed? [Single choice]

- No formal education
- Primary/elementary school
- Secondary/high school
- Vocational/technical training
- College/university (without a degree)
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Doctorate/PhD
- Prefer not to answer

["special interest" and academics/researchers survey only] We will be conducting follow-up research – through a series of focus groups – to understand in more detail the reasoning behind responses to this questionnaire. If you would be interested in participating in future research activities, please could you provide us with an email address that we can contact you on? Expressing an interest at this stage does not oblige you to take part in any future research activities.

You have reached the end of the survey. Thanks for your submission!

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